

ISic3471

I.Sicily inscription 3471

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

cippus

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2015.07.23 Metcalfe

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Gela

Place of origin (modern)

Gela

Provenance

contrada Manfria, necropolis

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Gela, Museo Archeologico

Regionale di Gela, inventory 38326

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI337233

1. [Π]ρημιτεῖβα

2. [χ]ρηστή, χαῖρε·

3. Μαννα τέκνον,

4. vac. χαῖρε· vac.

5. Μαννας γυναι-

6. κὶ καὶ τέκνω.

7.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175857
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Bibliography

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